

EFFICACY OF PATOLADI GUGGUL IN PAMA, KACHCHHU & CHARMADALA**Dr. Deodatta Bhadlikar¹, Dr. Devyani Bhadlikar², Dr. Shruti Saxena*³, Dr. Archana Pandey Jumle⁴, Rahul Jumle⁵**

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INTRODUCTION

The skin diseases in India are common problem. Owing to the illiteracy, un-cleanliness, poverty etc., a large portion of our community, is suffering from one or other skin disease.

According to Ayurveda, before-discussing the skin diseases, the following few Anatomical and Physiological points of significant value must be recapitulated.

1. The Chaaya and luster of the skin are due to the predominance of the respective Bhuta in it.
2. The expression or glow of the above changes, is due to a substance called 'Bhrajaka Pitta',
3. All the nutrients, drugs (applied externally), Sun rays etc., are digested and absorbed with the help of 'Bhrajaka Pitta.'
4. Embryologically the skin is formed as a cream over the boiling milk during the Paka of Shukra and Shonita.
5. Raktadhatu of our body while circulating through the skin gives colour, nutrition and sense of touch (Sparsha Jnana).
6. The poothi Gandha (Smell) of the skin is due to the pitta

vikara, and sweda vriddhi.

Classification of Skin Diseases

Diseases that manifest in the seven layers of Twak are only to be considered as Twak rogas. other skin diseases where, Twak, Rakta, Mamsa and Ambu one or more of these are Dooshyas.

The diseases that are claimed as skin diseases such as different varieties of kushtha, Kshudra Rogas, Blood diseases (as described in 24th chapter of Charaka Sambhita-sootra sthana) and the widely manifesting allergic skin diseases, are to be considered as Twak rogas.

In our samhitas, they have not discussed all the skin diseases at one place as a separate entity. Kushtha, Shwitra, Kshudra rogas (pertaining to skin), Sheeta — pitta, Udarda, Kotha, Visarpa, all such Chapters have discussed different/ skin diseases with the abovementioned names.

Apart from the above diseases, the Chapter of Krimiviyadhi gives us a clue, that our great seers also could have a thought that micro-organisms are also responsible for some skin diseases. In support of this statement Sushruta has gone still further and warns us that mutual contact in any form will give scope for the spreading of skin diseases.

Ayurveda has dealt with all the aspects of the skin diseases such as aetiology, Pathology; treatment exhaustively. To state briefly, the general Nidana of skin diseases in Ayurveda is identical with its contemporary system of modern medicine. It may be mentioned that interesting and thought-provoking factors like allergy, malnutrition, excessive exposure to Sun rays, lack of skin hygiene, infection and insect-bite etc. are included in its aetiology.

Common Aetiology

1. Viruddha Annapanam (Intake of incompatible food)
2. Atisantapa (Excessive exposure to Sun or heat)
3. Ati lavanamlanishevanam (Excessive consumption of salt and sour substances)
4. Panchakarmopachara (Irregular or incomplete undergoing of pancha karmas)
5. Papakarma etc. (Committing sinful deeds etc.)

Principles of Treatment

- (1) Shodhana. (2) Shamana

(1) **Shodhana**:- Shodhana is done in all cases with swadishta virechana choorna (Rasatantra sara sidha prayoga sangraha) 3 grams at bed time with luke-warm water. The same should be given twice weekly.

(2) Shamana

- (a) Sthanika chikitsa (local treatment)
- (b) Abhyantara chikitsa (Internal treatment)

(a) Sthanika Chikitsa

(a) 'Avalgujadi lepan' with 'Gomootra' applied externally over the affected part.

(b) Abhyantara Chikitsa

Since long some recipes are being tried extensively & the following simple compound preparation is found very effective in Pama, Kachchhu and Charmadala etc.

A compound name 'Patoladi Guggulu' which is a traditional preparation prepared as follows

1. Patola Choorna (Trichosanthus cucumerina Linn.) ore 1 part
2. Swarnmukhi leaves .choorna (Cassiaangustifolia Linn.) ... 4 part
3. Tamra Bhasma -+3 1/8 ~ part
4. Bhallataka - 1 part
5. Shuddha Guggulu - 6 parts

Method of Preparation

All the four drugs from (1 to 4) are mixed well and added in 6 parts of shuddha Guggulu & macerated well in Loha Khalva by adding goghruata to make it Pasty compound. 10 grain pills are made for administration.

Dose

1 Pill TDS given along with 'Guduchi Ksheeram', (obtained through Ksheera paka vidhi) for 10 to 15 days. During treatment the patient should be educated to observe Proper cleanliness, and observe 'Nidana Parivarjanam.'

CONCLUSION

Tamra Bhasma and Bhallataka are reputed as quick acting Krimihara and Twachya drugs. Patola and Guduchi are the ingredients of panchatiktas which are also effective and popular

remedies for skin diseases. Sennaisa laxative. Guggulu is Rasayana, & Lekhana, which in combination with the above drugs acts as the best curative. Ghrita due to its Samskaranuvartana, Rasayanatwa, Varnaprasadanatwa properties will naturally act as a synergistic agent in the above preparation.

Instead of attacking the causative infection like any other Ayurvedic medicine this preparation, prepares the Kshetra(body) not conducive for the growth of infection.

The composition will help to provide relief from the skin diseases.